

**19th International Conference on Chemistry
and the Environment - ICCE 2025**

Environmental Chemistry for Sustainability

E-Book of Abstracts

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Dear participants, welcome to Belgrade!

On behalf of the Division of Chemistry and the Environment (DCE) (<https://www.euchems.eu/divisions/chemistry-and-the-environment-2/>) of the European Association of the Chemical Societies (EuChemS) (<https://www.euchems.eu/>), the Serbian Chemical Society (<https://www.shd.org.rs/en/>), and the local organizing committee, it is our great pleasure and privilege to warmly welcome you to the 19th International Conference on Chemistry and the Environment (ICCE 2025).

This prestigious event, which gathers nearly 350 participants from across the globe is hosted by the Serbian Chemical Society with the support of the University of Belgrade and the University of Novi Sad.

At a time when continued scientific progress is essential to ensure a healthy environment and a sustainable future, ICCE 2025 addresses key challenges and emerging developments, advances knowledge and inspires action through the lens of Environmental Chemistry. In addition to the main program running in fourteen parallel sessions, ICCE 2025 will feature four pre-conference satellite events, each dedicated to current research priorities and strategic environmental topics and EuChemS DCE Career Award lecture by Terry Frank Bidleman from Sweden. The scientific program includes seven plenary lectures including two Distinguished Lectures from the American Chemical Society, and fourteen keynote lectures that introduce parallel sessions, comprising 175 oral and 156 poster presentations. A Special Editorial Panel Discussion, with editors from leading international scientific journals, will provide valuable insight into the evolving landscape of scientific publishing.

ICCE 2025 provides an excellent platform for networking, exchange of ideas and collaboration. Our collective mission is to deepen understanding of pollutant's cycling, and their fate and effects in the environment, while advancing pollution prevention and waste management. The latest developments in environmental analysis, pollution monitoring and risk assessment directly impact societal response to environmental challenges, which inevitably focus on various sustainability strategies. To be effective, these responses must be supported by excellent knowledge-based tools and societal inspiration, both offered by ICCE 2025.

We hope that you will not only enjoy the rich scientific program but also take-home memorable experiences from Serbia!

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City of Novi Sad ambient air: Benzo(a)pyrene associated health risk

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Inhaling polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) from the ambient air can have adverse effects on human health. The study aimed to investigate the content of benzo(a)pyrene (BaP) adsorbed on the inhalable fraction of particulate matter (PM₁₀; diameter up to 10 µm) and estimate the associated health risk for the inhabitants of the City of Novi Sad.

PM₁₀ sampling was performed at five monitoring sites (basic rural/urban, urban/suburban traffic, industrial) during 2023. Following ultra-sound extraction of PAHs, 1074 samples were analyzed using the GC-MS method.

The overall percentage of samples with quantified amounts of BaP was 45.1 (55.7% suburban-traffic > 51.0% industrial > 49.6% basic-rural > 44.0% urban-traffic > 28.2% basic-urban site). The lowest mean concentration was recorded at the basic urban site, while the highest was related to suburban traffic (0.5 and 1.0 ng/m³, respectively). When averaged, BaP level was 0.7 ng/m³. The annual level of BAP complied with regulatory requirements. The hazard quotient ranged from 0.24 on basic-rural to 0.48 on suburban-traffic sites, with a mean at 0.36 (averaging all the sites), revealing no serious health risk. Lifetime cancer risk was negligible for both children (from 4.1E-08 to 8.2E-08, mean 6.1E-08) and adults (from 1.6E-07 to 3.3E-07, mean 2.4E-07).

The study findings do not pose concerns related to human health. Nevertheless, a multitude of other PAH compounds present in ambient air and other sources of exposure to PAHs (mainly diet) have to be taken into account before reaching the final conclusion.

Keywords: air monitoring, PM₁₀, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, public health, risk assessment

References

[1] USEPA.IRIS Assessments. https://iris.epa.gov/ChemicalLanding/&substance_nmbr=136 (2017) Assessed 25 Jan 2025.